

PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES AND COACHING STYLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS: INPUT VARIABLES FOR THE PERFORMANCE OF ATHLETES IN DISTRICT OF ATIMONAN, QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

The researcher deliberately conducted this study to determine the professional qualities and coaching style of Physical Education teachers as variables of performance of athletes in the district of Atimonan, Quezon. A customized, self-fabricated questionnaire was used to gather data to complete the study. Atimonan District in Municipality of Atimonan, Quezon was the locale of the study comprises of 50 Physical Education Teachers from elementary and secondary education. The study indicates that perceived coaching styles of the respondents showed interest and enthusiasm for many sports, that athletes are engaged more in sports, offer a clear chain of command or supervision, and every aspect of the individual physical, mental-emotional, and spiritual are considered. The level of external performance of athletes in terms of skills is to understand the value and support of teamwork, to encourage and motivate team members to learn the value of sportsmanship, to know what their role in sport is, and to know the right mind leads to the right performance. There was significant correlation between the professional qualities of athletes' performance and coaching styles had meaningful correlation with athlete performers. The researcher is highly proposing a Development Plan that includes the association or organization of the physical education teachers in the study locale. It will serve as springboard to heighten their competencies as physical education teachers. Sports administrators and PE teacher-coaches may use the results of the study obtain on what coaching styles must be effective and what kind of coach our student-athletes need in order to enhanced their skill and be a better athlete.

Keywords: Physical Education, Professional Qualities, Coaching Styles, Athletes Performance